

KIMYO FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AFZALLIKLARI

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada kimyo o'qitish metodikasini rivojlantirish va yaxshilash, kimyo fani mavzulariga oid bilimlarni innovatsion yondashuvlar orqali tadbiq qilishni takomillashtirish va uni amalga oshirish qayd etilgan. Pedagogik faoliyatda turli xil tajriba va metodlardan foydalanishning dolzarbligi ko'rsatilgan.

Uchinchi renessans davri O'zbekistonimizda da yangilanishlar natijasida yangi innovatsion texnologiyalarning kirib kelishi ta'lim tizimini isloh qilishda juda muhim ahamiyatli ekanligini bilamiz . Ta'lim beruvchi tashkilotlarning moddiy texnik imkoniyatini kengaytirish, bilim berish samaradorligini xalqaro ta'lim standartlari darajasiga olib chiqish, malakali kadrlar tayyorlash tizimini zamon talablari va dunyo tajribasi asosida o'zgartirish imkoniyati yuzaga keldi. Innovatsiyaga har qanday turdagi yangilik sifatida emas, balki mavjud tizimning samaradorligini jiddiy ravishda oshiradigan omil sifatida qarashimiz lozim. Keng tarqalgan yangilash fikrlashlarga qaramasdan innovatsiyalar kashfiyotlardan farq qiladi. Ilm-fan va innovatsiyalar sohasidagi xalqaro reytinglarda mamlakat mavqeini oshirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlarni to'liq va samarali amalga oshirishga to'siq bo'layotgan tizimli kamchiliklarni aniqlash birgalikda muammolarni bartaraf etish bo'yicha yechim va takliflar ishlab chiqish oldimizdagi vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ilm-fan va innovatsiyalar sohasida raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirish bo'yicha ilmiy va startup loyihalar natijalarini sohalarga samarali joriy etilishi yuzasidan takliflar ishlab chiqish va bu ishlarni rivojlantirish uchun tadqiqot ishlarini yo'lga qo'yishimiz zarur. Ko'p yillar davomida olib borilgan pedagogik tadqiqotlar natijasida shaxs manbani o'zi mustaqil o'qiganda 10%, ma'lumotni eshitganda 20%, sodir bo'layotgan voqea, hodisa va jarayonni ko'rganda, ular to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlarni eshitganda 50%, ma'lumotlarni o'zi uzatganida 80%, o'zlashtirilgan bilimlarni o'z faoliyatiga tadbiq etganda esa 90% ma'lumotlarni yodda saqlash imkonini berishi aniqlangan. Demak shunday ekan, zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarga asoslangan dars mashg'ulotlarida talabalarda nafaqat tushunish, balki o'zlashtirilgan bilimlarni o'z faoliyatlarida qo'llay bilish, muammoli vaziyatlarda eng maqbul yechimlarni topa bilish kabi ko'nikmalar shakllanadi. Kimyoni o'qitishda eng ko'p tarqalgan va xususiyatga ega bo'lgan

zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar quyidagilar hisoblanadi: suhbat, bahs (munozara), o'yin, keys-stadi, loyihalar usuli, muammoli usul, aqliy hujum va boshqalar.

Dars jarayonida "Aqliy hujum" metodidan foydalanishda quyidagi qoidalarga amal qilish talab etiladi:

- o'zaro baholash va tanqidning mavjud emasligi;
- tanqid qilmang – har bir aytilgan fikr teng kuchga ega;

Gapirayotgan odamning gapini bo'lmangqanchalik fikrlar ko'p bo'lsa shunchalik yaxshi: yangi va kerakli fikrning paydo bo'lishi imkoniyati oshadi. Masalan, galogenlar mavzusidagi aqliy hujum savollari.

1. Galogenlarning davriy jadvaldagi o'rni va atomlarning tuzilishi
2. Galogenlar uchun xos fizik xossalari
3. Galogenlarning kimyoviy xossalari
4. Galogenlarning oksid va kislotalari
6. Nima uchun galogenlar nomini olgan. Bu nom ularning qaysi xossalari bilan bog'liq va bu xossalari ularning atom tuzilishi bilan qanday bog'lanishda ekanligini ayting?
7. Xlor va fluor, bromning muhim birikmalari va ularning bevosita amaliyotda ishlatilishini so'zlab bering?

Ma'ruza vaqtida qiziqarli kimyoviy tajribalarini ko'rsatish ham dars samaradorligini oshirishning muhim omillaridan biri hisoblanadi. Xususan, qo'rg'oshin (II)-asetat eritmasiga kaliy yodid eritmasini qo'shib, oltin rangidagi qo'rg'oshin yodid kristallarini olish ham qiziqarli tajribalardan biridir.

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